

Original Research Article

Undergraduate Nursing Students Satisfaction with Nursing Program

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Abstract

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Nurses are regarded as the heart of the healthcare system. They include the biggest ratio of labor force in every healthcare sets globally. In nursing, it is important to realize about students satisfaction with their undergraduate studies, as feelings of distress can be detected in students who are disappointed and can impact their academic lives, their professional future, their working setting and interactions, as well as people with whom they will work together and the care facilities they will deliver. The aim of the study was to assess the undergraduate nursing student's satisfaction with nursing program. A descriptive cross-sectional design would be used in this research study. The population for this study was the nursing students including BSN and Post-RN BS nursing from Lahore School of Nursing. Sample size was 134 for the study. Random sampling technique was used for this study. The likert scale questionnaire was used with 56 questions. Curriculum and instruction shows mean score ± 0.86 , clinical practices mean score is ± 0.901 , faculty of nursing facilities mean score is ± 0.89 , faculty of nursing climate mean score ± 0.895 , academic and personal development mean score was ± 0.8505 , follow-up of academic progress mean score was ± 0.8152 , causes that prevent students from being nurses mean score was ± 0.8784 . The study findings showed positive satisfaction of the students with the nursing program. This may reflect the future role of students in providing high quality nursing care. The nursing image should improve for the society and also for the students for being in nursing field.

Keywords: Nursing Program, Nursing, Students, Satisfaction, Undergraduate

INTRODUCTION

Nurses are regarded as the heart of the healthcare system. They encompass the biggest ratio of labor force in every healthcare sets globally (Hatamleh and Sorio, 2017). Satisfaction is understood as a mental state, in which results from authorization or disconfirmations of expectations with realism. Lacking a standard delineation of student's satisfaction is deliberated a multipart problem, even with its difficulty it has been considered as one of the greatest significant means in emerging high

quality education (Jaradeen, Jaradat, Abo Safi, Al Tarawneh, 2012).

Students' satisfaction as a short term response, resultant from an assessment of a students' learning practices. It had a positive impact on student loyalty (Weerasinghe and Fernando, 2017).

Education setting is deliberated as a significant indicator for the education platform. It has a crucial part in cultivating nursing student's development, competence,

critical intelligence, independency, understanding of psychological wellbeing and self-assurance. Education setting increase nursing student abilities for upcoming dares in future (Farooq, Rehman, Dias, & Hussain, 2018).

The course for undergraduates will be the new educating environment for the student's, which can affect their progress as academics and their professional prospect either positively or negatively. In nursing it is important to realize, how students view their undergraduate studies, as feelings of distress can be detected in students who are disappointed and can impact their academic lives, their professional future, their working setting and interactions, as well as people with whom they will work together and the care facilities they will deliver (Ramos et al., 2015).

Curriculum means the learning material that a school, college, universities prepared. It is very important to form the educational context of the student's satisfaction with the curriculum. Nursing faculties spent a lot of time to designing a curriculum and evaluating it to enhance nursing education and change patterns in the health care system (Ramasubramaniam, Grace, and Science, 2015).

Nurses are an important part of supplying the patient with health facilities, which is why communication is the key to forming a partnership between nurse-patient, nurse-doctor, nurse and other colleagues. The rise in nursing communication leads to minor health errors (Sibiya, 2018).

Participation of clinical teacher in clinical student learning is very significant. Clinical instructor's function and action encourages students to develop the clinical knowledge and skills. In order to attain high quality of clinical nursing education, student must be satisfied with character of the clinical instructor and give safe and sound care to the patient (Ismail et al., 2016).

In order to improve medical and healthcare knowledge, it is significant for nursing students to develop the computer abilities and organization should provide students with arranged computer facilities the digital learning tools included in the curriculum (Kirkova-Bogdanova, 2017). Computer usage has an encouraging effect on nursing management of subjective alteration. Computers will continue to affecting the condition of medicinal facilities, people and the call for nursing in the future (Shabnum, Afzal, Hussain, & Gilani). For nursing students, the field of training is significant, so preparation is vital for the student before consultation with the real patient. For the student degree of satisfaction with the organization and significant of the training period before and after study, the skill laboratory is appropriate for the students (Solvik, Struksnes, and Practice, 2018).

The clinical education environment has an effect on learning results and on preparation for practice and student satisfaction with the nursing field (Flott and Linden, 2016).

Professional competence is very significant feature of clinical success for health care providers, it is a dynamic process which influenced on circumstances (Makarem et al., 2019).

Feedback is very important to improve students learning. Feedback is relational offering educational and behavioral reactions to results. Feedback helps teacher to comprehend the satisfaction level of students understanding (Eriksson, Boistrup and Thornberg, 2018).

To inspire people towards any profession, the professional image is very significant. There is a positive and negative picture of the nursing profession that depends on the understanding of the nurses themselves. Public opinion, employment of students, healthcare authorities, long working hours, self-identity of the profession had an effect on the profession of nursing (Gunawan, Aunguroch, Sukarna, Efendi, and Studies, 2018).

Assessing every institution's progress is by the student's academic performance. In nursing the academic performance of nursing students is poor due to the low level of interested students, poor family history, bad professional image of nursing, poor services available, relationship between student and instructor is poor (Dube and Mlotshwa, 2018).

Problem Statement

Research in "student satisfaction with nursing program" was conducted in Jordan 2012, the study concentrated on the student's clinical training and abilities for the future profession. Another study on nursing student's satisfaction with the field of study was conducted in Iran 2014, this study focused on the student's emotional and mental problems. In Pakistan the studies conducted on the clinical learning satisfaction and educational environment. Having interest in the "undergraduate nursing student's satisfaction with nursing program" there was no study conducted on this topic in Pakistan and the study focuses on the causes that prevent a students from being in the field of nursing and would like to discuss the educational and clinical nursing environment that reflect student nurses. These variables were not clearly discussed in the previous researches.

Student satisfaction with their education is the symbol of effective attainment of organization. Student satisfaction response helps to examine the facilities delivered by an institution and teaching, learning setting, approaches and services. Global researcher agreed that the response of student's satisfaction will contribute to progress educational organization (Razinkina et al., 2018). Providing the patient with an excellent care is the nursing organization's first importance, so the satisfaction with nursing practices is important for the student to improve their skills. It was investigated that quality of care depends on job or field satisfaction, which includes work

environment, pressure, pay, scheduling of workers, education program etc (Farman, Kousar, Hussain, Waqas, and Gillani). The problem which is discussing in this study is the satisfaction level of undergraduate nursing students with the educational and clinical environment and practices, causes that prevent students to choose nursing profession and improve the nurse's image in their work area.

Significance of Study

Importance of the research is to rise the satisfaction level of student nurses involvement in education, indications to continuous improvements to educational establishment's services, and use these growths to make significant improvements in the supply characteristics (Saif & Science, 2014). Satisfaction with the nursing field allows a student nurses to develop skills in patient care, expert declaration, and the practices of problem solving, psychomotor skills, and critical thinking. They also increase their socialization and practiced role self-assurance. But if learner nurses were not satisfied with their field they cannot achieve their goals and cannot be expert in their field of studies (Khalil, Majeed, Bio, and Gilani, 2017). Have interest with this study is to assess the satisfaction level of student nurses, this study is very important for the nursing students about the satisfaction with their field of nursing for the future clinical practices and it is important for the department of nursing to enhance the educational environment more proficient for student's and improve the level of satisfaction by providing all the facilities for the student nurses. This study will help the University of Lahore to identify the causes which effect the satisfaction level of students, because the student's dissatisfaction with the academic and clinical environment downs the university reputation.

Objective

To assess the undergraduate nursing student's satisfaction with nursing program

Conceptual Framework

Chen, Farmer, Barber, and Wayman, (2012) established the theoretical model of Curriculum, facility, social collaboration and environment (CFSE). This model is useful to measure the satisfaction level of undergraduate nursing student in the field of study. This model specifies that student satisfaction is centered on the student collaboration with environment, teachers and nursing student affected by these four components, social collaboration, learning environment such as skill lab, content, teaching strategies. The relationship of this

model with this study is that these variables are also discussed in this study like curriculum is very important for the student's academic satisfaction. Curriculum plays a vital role to enhance nursing education and change patterns in the health care system. Student's satisfaction with their clinical and academic faculties is also significant for their professional grooming and it also helps to increase their interest with the learning. Clinical instructor's function and action encourages students to develop the clinical knowledge and skills. Social collaboration is vital for the nursing students because their interaction with the social environment is excessive. During their training students learn how to communicate with people and social interaction. Nursing students need to understand a supportive medical and educational environment that honors professional values and belief. Figure 1

METHODOLOGY

Study Design

A descriptive cross-sectional design would be used in this research study.

Study Site

This study would be conducted in the University of Lahore.

Settings

The study would be conducted in the Lahore School of Nursing, The University of Lahore.

Target population

The population for this study was the nursing students including BSN and Post-RN BS nursing from Lahore School of Nursing. The total population of BSN and Post-RN BS nursing students were 202. Solvin's sampling formula was used to find the sample size which was 134 for this study.

Data Collection Plan

The likert scale questionnaire was used to assess the satisfaction level of undergraduate nursing students with the nursing program. Random sampling technique used for this study. The questionnaire was distributed among BSN and Post -RN BS nursing students in the Lahore School of Nursing.

Figure: The CFSE Model for Assessing Student Satisfaction: Curriculum, Faculty, Social Interaction, and Environment

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Figure 1

Equipment

In this study, the questionnaire was adopted by Najah et al. (2012) and Wajed et al. (2017). The demographic data consist of 4 questions and likert scale questionnaire was used with 56 questions with 5 options named as strongly dissatisfied, dissatisfied, neither, satisfied, strongly satisfied.

Validity and Reliability

A pilot study was conducted to determine the instrument's psychometric assessment. The Cronbach's Alpha reliability rating of the whole instrument is 0.94.

Ethical Consideration

- All written informed consent attached will be obtained from all the respondents.
- All data collection and information would be kept private.
- Throughout the study, participant's identity would be private.
- The subjects would be informed that the study procedure does not present any disadvantages or risk.

- They would also be informed that during the study process they would be free to withdraw at any time.
- The data was kept in under the key and locked while the keys are kept in hand. It will be kept under password in laptop.

Data Analysis

Data analyzed on SPSS version 21.0 frequencies, percentage, mean and standard deviation applied on individual item. Data was collected through questionnaire. Distributed in 134 participants.

RESULTS

Part-I Demographic Data

The participant's frequency and percentage of gender, age, study year and accumulative average results shown in Table 1. The results of demographic data shows that total male students were 20.1% and female students were 79.9% fill the survey questionnaire and participate in this study. The maximum 38.1% of participants fall in the age of 19-21 and the minimum 19.4% fall in the age of 22-24%. The majority of students which participate in the study were 37.3% from second year and minimum

Table 1. Demographic Data

Gender	f	%
Male	27	20.1
Female	107	79.9
Total	134	100.0
Age		
16-18Years	29	21.6
19-21 Years	51	38.1
22-24 Years	26	19.4
25-27 Years	28	20.9
Total	134	100.0
Study year		
First Year	38	28.4
Second Year	50	37.3
Third Year	33	24.6
Fourth Year	13	9.7
Total	134	100.0
Accumulative average		
Excellent	12	9.0
Very good	31	23.1
Good	59	44.0
Satisfactory	32	23.9
Total	134	100.0

Table 2. The percentage, frequencies, mean and standard deviation of undergraduate nursing student's satisfaction with nursing program

Sr. no	Statements	Strongly dissatisfied		Dissatisfied		Neither		Satisfied		Strongly satisfied		mean	s.d
		f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%		
	Curriculum and Instruction												
1	Faculty provide me with the course syllabus	4	3.0	9	6.7	27	20.1	69	51.5	25	18.7	3.76	.935
2	Faculty inform me of grading method	1	.7	14	10.4	43	32.1	65	48.5	11	8.2	3.53	.820
	Clinical Practices												
3	Instructors are concerned about my safety	4	3.0	.7	3.0	38	28.4	66	49.3	22	16.4	3.73	.877
4	Instructors are accessible	1	.7	9	6.7	43	32.1	67	50.0	14	10.4	3.63	.792
	Faculty of Nursing Facilities												
5	The photocopying service was available	8	6.0	7	5.2	15	11.2	72	53.7	32	23.9	3.84	1.039
6	Library time suits me	5	3.7	8	6.0	26	19.4	78	58.2	17	12.7	3.70	.901
	Faculty of Nursing Climate												
7	Faculty of nursing employees treat me with respect	9	6.7	5	3.7	21	15.7	75	56.0	24	17.9	3.75	1.016
8	Cheating was a problem in this course	4	3.0	7	5.2	50	37.3	63	47.0	10	7.5	3.51	.829
	Academic and Personal Development												
9	I communicate properly	3	2.2	8	6.0	20	14.9	88	65.7	15	11.2	3.78	.810

Table 2. Continue

10	Faculty help me to develop professional competence	1	.7	5	3.7	39	29.1	77	57.5	12	9.0	3.70	.715
Follow-up of Academic Progress													
11	Faculty help students to improve their academic	4	3.0	2	1.5	20	14.9	90	67.2	18	13.4	3.87	.774
12	Faculty follow-up my academic performance	3	2.2	6	4.5	47	35.1	67	50.0	11	8.2	3.57	.774
Causes that prevent students from being nurses													
13	Community does not appreciate nursing profession	2	1.5	4	3.0	24	17.9	79	59.0	25	18.7	3.90	.784
14	Majority of people down grade nurses	1	.7	4	3.0	31	23.1	80	59.7	18	13.4	3.82	.724

9.7% from the fourth year. 44.0% students accumulative average was good and only 9.0% of students had excellent results.

Part II: The percentages, frequencies, mean and standard deviation of undergraduate nursing student's satisfaction with nursing program

The Table 2 shows likert scale questionnaire results it gives the description about: curriculum and instruction shows 56.7% students were satisfied and .7% were dissatisfied and the overall mean score of the variable was ± 0.86 , clinical practices shows 53.7% students were satisfied and .7% were dissatisfied and the overall mean score of variable was ± 0.901 , faculty of nursing facilities shows 65.7% students were satisfied and .7% dissatisfied and the overall mean score of variable was ± 0.89 , faculty of nursing climate 58.2% of students were satisfied and 3.0% dissatisfied and the overall mean score of variable was ± 0.895 , academic and personal development 65.7% students were satisfied and .7% were dissatisfied and the overall mean score of variable was ± 0.8505 , follow-up of academic progress 67.2% of students were satisfied and 1.5% of students were dissatisfied and the overall mean score of variable was ± 0.8152 , causes that prevent students from being nurses 59.7% students shows satisfied results and .7% were dissatisfied and the overall mean score of variable was ± 0.8784 .

DISCUSSION

The study results show that undergraduate nursing

student's satisfaction with nursing program was satisfied. Maximum numbers of students were satisfied with curriculum and instruction. The other study also shows similar findings that strategic plan for curriculum will prepare nursing students for new professional position within creative care model (Schwendimann et al., 2019). This study shows high percentage of students was satisfied with clinical practices. The researches conferring that students were minimum satisfied with the clinical practices at the university is effective in inspiring and education worth elevation (HAKIM and Professionalism, 2014). This study shows the high level of students satisfaction in the faculty of nursing facilities because all of services available in the university for students. One of the study shows the related results that students had all facilities available will increases satisfaction with clinical learning (Papastavrou et al., 2016). This study revealed the extreme students satisfaction with the nursing climate. Other researchers stated that nurses are the main person establishes the good atmosphere of clinical area. Nursing students need to understand a supportive medical and educational environment that honors professional values and belief (de Swardt et al., 2017). Study stated that student academic presentation is affected by the following factors like clinical teacher, university, family (Fajar et al., 2019). This study shows the increased satisfaction of students with academic and personal development within nursing field, it also shows that high level of nursing students satisfied with the follow-up of academic progress. The other studies results similar Muliira, Natarajan, Van Der Colff, (2017) stated that students and faculty equally participate in the academic incivility, it increases student's academic and clinical performance, students were satisfied with the involvement of instructor and receive feedback on their

studies. Maximum students were satisfied in this study about the causes that prevent students from being in nursing field. The other studies results was similar, lesser interest in the settlement of clinical practice was associated with increased stress in nursing student (Perng, Sung, Chen, Lee, & Koo, 2019). Because of the poor thinking of society nursing students were dissatisfied with their profession because they need respect which was not given by society (Mishra, 2015). Furthermore, the overall results of this study shows that high percentage of students were satisfied with all the facilities available in university, teachers involvement, clinical and academic environment, curriculum. Very minimum amount of students were dissatisfied. The maximum students were think that the nursing image was not good and different factors affect the nursing image.

CONCLUSION

The study findings showed positive satisfaction of the students with the nursing program. This may reflect the future role of students in providing high quality nursing care. The nursing image should improve for the society and also for the students for being in nursing field. Students know the importance of nursing for promoting their field.

Only one nursing institute was reviewed in this study so the results cannot be generalized.

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